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EFFECTIVENESS OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING TYPES IN ENHANCING DISCIPLINE
AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OLOKURTO DIVISION,
NAROK, COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract

While education is expected to change the behaviour of learners positively by moulding them into self-respecting and self-reliant individuals, discipline related issues have been at the fore of educational debates as students encounter challenges associated with adolescence. Cases of truancy, drug abuse, immorality, destruction of property and loss of life, are however, indicators of the existence of a conflict between educational aims and discipline among secondary school students. This is despite the provision of guidance and counselling services in schools, hence the need to examine the effectiveness of guidance and counselling in enhancing discipline among secondary school students. The objective of study was to establish the effectiveness of guidance and counselling types employed towards enhancing discipline among secondary school students in Olokurto Division, Narok County, Kenya. Descriptive survey design was employed in the study and questionnaire used obtain data from respondents. Person centred theory advanced by Carl Rogers guided the study. The study population comprised 861 students, 12 teacher counsellors and 6 deputy principals drawn from the six public secondary schools in the division. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were employed to sample 129 students for the study. Schools, deputy principals and teacher counsellors in the division were purposively sampled. Using test-retest method, the instruments yielded a reliability schools coefficient of $r = 0.76$, thus accepted for the study. Data were analyzed using the SPSS software version 20.0 and presented in tables, charts, graphs, means, frequencies and percentages. The study established that schools employed individual, peer and group types to counsel students but effectiveness had not been attained due to lack of counselling knowledge, skills and techniques due to the low training levels of teacher counsellors. Findings and recommendations of this study, if implemented will be useful to policy makers in the Ministry of Education Science and Technology, heads of secondary schools, counselling personnel and students through improved application of guidance and counselling types.

Key words: Effectiveness, Peer/ Individual/Group Counselling, Discipline, Narok County

Introduction

Discipline related issues have been at the forefront of education debates where most problems that students encounter are associated with their developmental changes that adolescent go through. During this period, adolescents undergo emotional and physical changes, emotional traumas and exhibit behavioural problems which are not only

harmful for their health but are also in conflict with school expectation and social norms (Kinara, 2003). This being a trying period to their physical, emotional, psychological and academic development, the students try all sorts of adjustment mechanisms to get their needs fulfilled (Mangal, 2007).

Adolescent stages have been documented as societal concerns for centuries, thus calling on parents, pastors, teachers, peers and significant others to assist students by providing effective guidance and counselling to forestall destruction, injuries and loss of life. Fieldman and Elliot (1990) posit that, these behavioural challenges are associated with negative health, school administrators' failure, drug addiction, sexuality and associated infections, pregnancy, injury and death. The study concurs with their observation since drug and substance addiction has ruined the health, academic achievement and careers of many. Effective guidance and counselling should enable students deal with psychological problems that they may experience and make rational decisions on how to solve or cope with the challenges that they may encounter. Republic of Kenya (1999) recommends that guidance and counselling in educational institutions be an active and available service on daily basis to all students.

Objective

Establish the effectiveness of the types of guidance and counselling employed towards enhancing discipline among secondary school students in Olokurto Division.

Literature Review

Effectiveness of the Types of Guidance and Counselling in Enhancing Discipline

Human needs and lifestyle necessitate new inventions and strategies to help them cope or adjust to the changing situations. Guidance and counselling types used in schools to enhance discipline include peer, individual and group counselling. Initially, guidance and counselling focused on career development, but contemporary socio-economic issues such as employment, drug abuse, unstable families and truancy among others have necessitated the incorporation of professional guidance and counselling in educational institutions. Ayieko

(1988) observes that guidance and counselling plays a pivotal role in student behaviour management and correction in schools. Ayieko's study however failed to show how this could be applied in enhancing discipline in relation to academic achievement and the strategies that should be employed. Discipline and academic performance are closely related. Soet (2005) observes that learning without discipline is joyless, without direction was senseless and was of the opinion that discipline was crucial and basic to everything else in the classroom.

Guidance and counselling when effectively delivered, helps to develop an individual who is more productive, happier and well-adjusted to the environment, thus when orientation and adaptive services are provided they assist students to adjust to their school environment during the transition period. According to Hawkins and Carlton (1990) well-adjusted students who developed positive affiliation on social bond with their school are more likely to remain academically engaged thus, less likely to become involved in school misconduct and other anti-social behaviour than students who develop negative affiliation. It is important to note that the following types of counselling which this study explored are crucial to examining the effectiveness of guidance and counselling in enhancing discipline among secondary school students.

Effectiveness of Peer Counselling in Enhancing Discipline among Students

This is a method where peer counsellors and their clients see each other as equals regardless of their different backgrounds. It involves handling of individuals who could be of the same age, have same point of interest or share needs irrespective of their backgrounds and status. Kariuki (2002) in a study on peer counselling observes that peer counsellors in schools help improve academic achievement since students help each other socially,

psychologically and academically. The study agrees with Kariuki's assertion adding that students heavily conform to groups' standards and tend to value each other's opinion during their stay together. Teachers and counsellors are therefore supposed to utilize these groups to instill discipline and skills so that in their long times together, they are able to share moral skills. They need to use such groupings to nurture good behaviour and instill a sense of hard work among students for improved academic achievement.

Dobbins (2004) posits that many schools train peer counsellors on educational counselling service and social relationship but fails to point out the criteria of selecting those to be trained as peer counsellors since not every other person can be a counsellor. The training provides students with free interaction time with peer counsellors, thus giving them an atmosphere of sharing their feelings and experiences, thought and problems freely. Kilgariff (1999) argues that peer counsellors act as liaisons to student counselling by identifying problems and making referrals and encouraging others to seek professional help. This calls for proper training of peer counsellors to equip them with counselling skills, thus effectively assist other students. Gichunge (1996) posits that in a dynamic world of uncertainty and increasing changes and unknown future careers choice, students need to acquire skills that enable them overcome social and emotional problems that tend to militate against peaceful learning with other students. Encouraging the training of peer counsellors and ensuring that students receive effective counselling services throughout their stay in school would be a sure way of enhancing discipline.

Nyaga (2011) asserts that peer counsellors assist other students by clarifying thoughts and feelings, exploring options or providing needed information while Davidoff (1987) observes that peer influence on adolescent development is

evident since teenagers spend most of their time together and form cliques or groupings, share their interests and discuss how to find new friends. Lutomia and Sikolia (2002) state that peer counselling involves counselling students of the same age, interests and goals. In this respect students perceived each other as equals and teacher counsellors need to train these peers to counsel fellow student since they have a lot of influence on each other. They can be used to pass information after a teachers meeting since it is a time saving method of guidance and counselling and helps many individuals with common interests or needs especially during crisis. Peer counsellors enable students to be free to seek assistance, thus making it advantageous since they relate without the age gap that is at times a problem between teachers and students.

Effectiveness of Individual Counselling in Enhancing Discipline among Students

According to Gibson and Mariane (2006) individual counselling has since the early days of the counselling movement been identified as an important effective tool in the guidance and counselling process. Individual refers to a 'one - to - one' relationship involving a counsellor and counselee and focuses on some aspects of the client's adjustment, developmental or decision making needs. Nyaga (2011) posits that the client and counsellor focus on attaining goals which include behaviour change as the relationship becomes more authentic, collaborative and instructive. The process provides a relationship and communication base, from which the student develops understanding, explores possibilities and initiates change towards desired social norms in relation to the school setting.

The interactional process requires at least two people who affect each other. In certain interactions the counsellor is capable of modifying or enabling the client change behaviour to socially desirable levels. This could be achieved through proper and effective

delivery of guidance and counselling services to the students. Teacher counsellors therefore have the responsibility of providing effective guidance and counselling services that enable students to overcome maladaptive issues which are likely to affect their discipline and academic achievement. To realize the potential benefits of the counselling relationship, the students must be made to take up some responsibilities to participate fully, co-operatively and willingly (Gibson & Mariane, 2006). Teachers and counsellors need to counsel students and make them aware of the dangers associated with drug and substance abuse since they are also associated with indiscipline and poor academic achievement. They should instill a sense of hard work among students to avoid repeating classes and assist them to identify points of crisis as they develop self-knowledge that will eventually help them set realistic goals and plans which are realistic in life.

Effectiveness of Group Counselling in Enhancement Discipline among Students

The purpose of group therapy is to increase members' knowledge of themselves and others, help members clarify changes they must make in their life and provide members with tools they need to make the desired changes (Robert & Riley, 2009). Group counselling comprises six to twelve members that offer multiple relationships to assist each individual in growth and problem solving unlike the individual therapy that has the counsellor and the counselee. Group therapy encourages interaction and facilitates deeper self-understanding and acceptance because an environment of mutual respect that enables individuals to loosen their defenses sufficiently to explore both the meaning of behaviour and new ways of behaving.

Nyaga (2011) observes that group counselling can be useful to students having special problems that affect the development of their

competences and behaviour. Every member in the group is offered an opportunity to help others and this makes it a powerful therapeutic tool in guidance and counselling that greatly enhances members self-esteem and self-worth. Each of the group members acts as substitute for siblings seeking attention and affection from the leader and forming subgroups and coalitions with other members. Through sharing of information, enormous relief of tension accompanies the recognition that they are not alone and feedback to each other about the appropriateness of the others behaviour, is relayed to all, thus helping in improving discipline among group members.

Weinberg (1975) argues that the best way to make maximum use of the group counselling is to increase meaningful legitimate patterns of behaviour and recommended the formation of opportunity structures aimed at alleviating the strains that motivate people to engage in undesirable patterns. The study however notes that this can be achieved through the proper use of the school rules and opening adequate communication avenues between students and the school administration. The teacher counsellor therefore will need to have excellent communication skills and an understanding of student behaviour to ensure that information flow is not interrupted by portraying trust to their students. Kombo (1998) asserts that the readiness on the part of the administration to negotiate with students by including them in decision making plays a pre-emptive role and dissipates tension that could lead to indiscipline among students. The researcher observes that the assertion would make guidance and counselling more effective if the school administration could agree to incorporate the students in some levels of decision making to make them own the said ventures.

Group therapy is viewed as family unit with a group of people who are linked by a bond or a force that unites members who share life or a common destiny. Muroki and Edwin (2009)

assert that the family teaches virtues to its members and help them to do what they should as honest, royal, generously and humbly struggling to improve their character. They further observe that group counselling facilitates cooperation among members as they work towards achieving a particular goal. Schools on the other hand, are supposed to establish homelike environments to address students' needs in a conducive and acceptable environment thus give all an opportunity for interaction, self-disclosure and receive feedback. With the help of the teacher counsellor, departmental heads and the school administration, family units can be based on classes or houses for moral support, thus promoting the role of guidance and counselling in enhancing discipline among students. This should be done at definite times to ensure non infringement of other school programmes and the teacher counsellor in collaboration with other teachers can formulate themes to act as guiding principles for discussions.

Njoya (2000) in support of the family unit observes that, 'when the student enjoys justice and respect within the grouping, he or she extends this joy to others in the set up. Holding regular meetings to advice students on all matters concerning their development, growth and career choices in addition to prospects of joining particular institution gives students hope and desire to perform, hence the need to display relevant information at strategic points, (Muroki & Edwin (2009). Griffin (1996) observes that communication between teachers on one hand, and learners, parents and the community at large makes learning stress free and reduces possibility learning stress free and reduces the possibility of strikes. This study notes that appropriate channels of communication among members in given group of people can be used to help enhance discipline and guidance and counselling is one of them.

Wangombe (2008) in her research on 'Adolescence behavioural problems' observes that high handed administration, lack of guidance and use of rigid rules as some of the causes for the increasing cases of student unrest and indiscipline. This she blames on lack of information and poor communication skills on the part of the administration and this makes the school appear to be a hostile environment for students. Butter (1998) argues that providing students with safe environments enhances character development and in the long run promotes enhanced discipline among students and the entire school community. The study notes that, to provide a safe environment, the teacher counsellor is expected to use collaborative skills to ensure there is proper communication, not only between the counsellor and counselee but also between the administration and the school community.

Research Methodology

The study was conducted in the 6 public secondary schools in Olokurto Division, Narok County with a target population of 861 comprised of form one to form four boys and girls students, 12 teacher counsellors and 6 deputy principals. Male and female teacher counsellors were purposively sampled from each school to ensure gender representation. Teacher counsellors participated in the study because they provide guidance and counselling services to students. Stratified sampling technique was employed to sample student and classes formed the strata. Kothari (2004) posits that stratified sampling yields more reliable and detailed data ensuring that no sub-population is omitted (Orodho, 2004). Simple random sampling technique was then employed to sample students in each stratum thus offer every student had an equal chance to participate in the study.

Descriptive survey design was employed in the study to establish the effectiveness of types of guidance and counselling employed to enhance

discipline among secondary school students. Gay, Mills and Airasian (2009) observe that descriptive survey involves describing, analyzing and assessing attitudes, opinions towards individuals, organizations and procedures. Rubin and Babbie (2010) argue that surveys help make more generalized findings. This design was found appropriate since the study was seeking information concerning the current status on the effectiveness of guidance and counselling in enhancing discipline among students in Olokurto Division of Narok County. Questionnaires with multiple responses were administered to respondents yielding a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.76$ in a test retest method thus accepted for the study. Qualitative data from the responses were organized thematically according to research objective and quantitative data analysis done to generate frequencies and percentages with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Discussions were presented in tables, charts, graphs, means, percentages and frequencies.

Results and Discussions

Demographic information of Respondents

Respondents of the study comprised male and female students, teacher counsellors and deputy principals.

Students' Demographic Information

The researcher sought to establish the population of the respondents according to gender in order to allocate an equitable sample representation to categories represented in the study. Figure 1 indicates that male students were more than female 78 (61.40%) and 49 (38.60%) respectively. Disparity indicates there were issues that negatively affected enrolment of students, especially girls. The researcher attributed the low enrolment of students to the inability of schools to retain them due to the numerous indiscipline cases such as pregnancies among girls, cultural practices in the community and the resultant poor academic results in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE).

Gender of Students

Figure 1 indicates low enrolment of female students which the study attributes to indiscipline cases reported (D.E.O.'s Office 2012). Retention rates were low due to girls' pregnancies while riots and strikes were a common occurrence.

Age Brackets of Students

Figure 2 indicates that 68.0% of the students were adolescents in the 16 -19 years age bracket with only 5.5% in the over 20 years - age bracket. The 13- 15 years age bracket were 26.5%. Students within the indicated age brackets

Figure 2: Age brackets of Students

Class and School Category of Respondents

Table 1 indicates that 93 (73.2%) of the students were in mixed boarding schools compared to 34 (26.8%) who were in day schools and thus in constant contact with their relatives. It further indicates that 30.7% of the respondents were in form one, 26.0% in form two, 24.4% in form three and 18.9%. This means that most of the students were in the transitional stage: some exiting primary school life to join form one in new environments, thus requiring counselling to enable them adjust to new life away from their relatives.

Table 1

Class and school category of Respondents

Class	Frequency	Percentage
Form 1	39	30.70
Form 2	33	26.00
Form 3	31	24.40
Form 4	24	18.90

Figure 1: Gender of Students

require continuous guidance to help them cope with challenges they encounter. Adolescence is considered to be a trying period especially for students in regard to their physical, emotional, psychological and academic development, thus a delicate stage (Mangal, 2007). In affirming Mangal's assertion, Wanjiku (2004) posits that rioting students in Makueni cried out that they required someone to listen to them while Wangombe (2008) posits that adolescents perceive themselves as adults in the society. The researcher's note that adolescents require guidance and counselling to help them adjust to the different situations they may find themselves in.

From the students' demographic information, it is evident that there was high enrolment of students in form one and decreased as they moved towards fourth form. The number of female students had also decreased significantly from 111 students in form one to 63 in form four a decline of 43% for girls and 31% for boys. The researcher attributed the poor retention rate to indiscipline cases that include drug and substance abuse and cultural activities that lead to early marriage of girls while boys joined moranism (UNESCO, 2005).

School Category	Frequency	Percentage
Mixed Boarding	93	73.20
Mixed Day	34	26.80
Others	0	0.00
Total	127	100%

Teacher Counsellors' Demographic Information

Teacher counsellors' demographic information included age brackets, gender, and training levels school category.

Figure 3 shows that 60% of the teacher counsellors were within 25- 30 age bracket while 20% of the counsellors were in the 31- 35 and the 36 -40 years age brackets respectively. None of the teacher counsellors was over 40 years.

The researcher observes that most of teacher counsellors had neither acquired the adequate

knowledge, skills and techniques in guidance and counselling nor experience in the provision of counselling services due to their age and low training levels. The study concurs with Mutie and Ndambuki, (2004) and Republic of Kenya (1964) who advocate for the training of counsellors and inclusion of guidance and counselling in the teachers' training curriculum respectively.

Figure 3: Age Brackets of Teacher Counsellors

Gender of Teacher Counsellors

Figure 4 shows that 60% of the counsellors were female while 40% were male teachers. Most students may not to receive counselling as

frequently as they should due to gender disparity and population of teacher counsellors thus affecting discipline levels among students.

This implied that the few male teachers available were not adequate to effectively offer counselling to students and this could compromise discipline among students especially in the area of study since cultural activities and traditional beliefs did not recognize the authority of women. For instance, moranism as a rite of passage was highly valued

than education among boys while girls were married off at an early age (UNESCO, 2005).

Findings indicate that there was a shortage of guidance and counselling personnel in schools since the available counsellors could not effectively provide guidance and counselling services to 861 students in Olokurto division alongside attending to their teaching duties.

Figure 4: Gender of Teacher Counsellors Training Levels of Teacher Counsellors

Table 2 shows that 80% of teacher counsellors had received training at certificate level while 20% had received induction courses only. Percentages imply that most teacher counsellors had acquired basic knowledge in guidance and counselling. They however could not effectively address the issues and challenges that students encounter in their daily school life as they had not acquired adequate knowledge, skills and techniques.

Mangal (2007) describes adolescence as a trying period to the physical, emotional, psychological and academic development of students, thus they try all sorts of adjustment mechanisms to get their needs fulfilled. The study notes that students require continuous guidance and counselling to help them cope with challenging issues. This however was not happening as teacher counsellors had not acquired adequate training in counselling.

Table 2: Training Levels of Teacher Counsellors

Training Level in Guidance and Counselling	Frequency	Percentage
Induction Course	2	20
Certificate	8	80
Other Levels	0	0
Total	10	100

Deputy Principals’ Demographic Information

In most schools it is the deputy principal who handles all indiscipline cases. They are therefore expected to have acquired some training in

guidance and counselling in order to compliment teacher counsellors’ efforts of delivering counselling services to the students towards enhancing discipline among students.

Deputy Principals' Levels of Training in Guidance and Counselling

Table 3 shows that 80% of the deputy principals had acquired training at various levels; induction, certificate, diploma and degree and only one without any training. The study notes that most of the deputy principals had acquired basic knowledge in guidance and counselling they could apply as they performed their duties. With the increased demand for high academic

achievement, technological advancement, socio-cultural and socio-economic changes in the society, guidance and counselling was required in order to equip students with skills, attitudes and knowledge that would them adjust and cope with the challenges.

Table 3: Deputy Principals' Training Levels in Guidance and Counselling

Level of Training in Counselling	Frequency	Percentage
Induction Course	1	20
Certificate	1	20
Diploma	1	20
Degree	1	20
Not trained	1	20
Other levels	0	0
Total	5	100%

Length of service as Deputy Principals

The study sought to establish the duration deputy principals had served in that position since they were mainly in charge of discipline issues in their schools. Table 4 indicates that 80% of the respondents had served as deputy principals for between one and five years, one for between six to ten years and none had served in the position for over ten years.

Table 4: Length of service as Deputy Principals

Years of service	Frequency	Percentage
1 -5 years	4	80
6 - 10 years	1	20
Over 10 years	0	0
Total	5	100%

Mutie and Ndambuki (2004) argue that guidance and counselling assists clients move towards a greater level of self-acceptance and

self-understanding thus leading them towards awareness of their abilities and limitations. Mbithi (1999) on the other hand observes that

guidance and counselling aims at helping clients find solutions to the issues and challenges they continuously faced.

Effectiveness of Peer Counselling in Enhancing Discipline among Students

The study sought to establish the effectiveness of peer counselling in enhancing discipline in selected problem areas. Findings presented in table 5 indicate that 37% of the students strongly agreed that peer type of counselling had been effective in reducing cases of bullying and sneaking. The fact that 17.7% of the students disagreed and 10.2% strongly disagreed that peer counsellors were effective in helping reduce strikes and riots implies that there was minimal interaction between peer counsellors and other students.

The students' responses were an indication that peer counsellors had received little or no training and therefore lacked the prerequisite knowledge and skills to address the challenges encountered by other students. Dobbins (2004)

observes that many schools train peer counsellors on educational counselling and social relationship which provides students with interaction time with their peers thus giving them an atmosphere of sharing their feelings, thoughts and problems freely. Though Nyaga (2011) posits that peer counsellors assist other students by clarifying thoughts and feelings, exploring options or providing needed information, lack of counselling knowledge and skills could lead to ineffective delivery of the services. This therefore requires that peer counsellors be equipped with knowledge and skills that can enable them handle issues that other students encounter.

The study notes that peer counsellors' role as liaisons between students and teachers was greatly eroded posing a threat to them and discipline levels among students. Adequate training for peer counsellors could help to change the students' attitude towards peer counselling, thus enhance discipline among students.

Table 5: Effectiveness of Peer Counselling in Enhancing Discipline among Students

Statements	Responses (percent)					TOTAL
	SA	A	NS	D	SD	
Peer counsellors in my school help students to obey school rules , thus enhance discipline	47.7	34.6	4.7	11.8	1.6	100.0 (127)
Peer counsellors helped reduce cases of bullying and sneaking	37.0	41.8	7.1	10.2	3.9	100.0 (127)
Cases of drug and substance abuse reduced because of peer counsellors service delivery	49.6	34.7	3.1	4.7	7.9	100.0 (127)
Peer counsellors act as liaisons between students and school authorities, thus help stall riots	18.1	40.9	13.4	17.7	10.2	100.0 (127)

Effectiveness of Individual Counselling in Enhancing discipline among Students

Responses as presented in Table 6 indicate that 61.4% of the students strongly agreed that individual counselling was effective in reducing cases of school dropout. Another 46.5% strongly agreed that the direct relationship offered through individual counselling had been

effective in helping them change behaviour positively while 7.1% were not sure. On failure to complete assignments 45.7% strongly agreed that cases had reduced and a further 34.6% agreed 11.0% were not sure. The researcher notes that students attended individual

counselling because of the close interaction with the counsellor meaning they were sensitive to personal information and therefore required confidentiality by seeking individual counselling. To realize the potential benefits of

the counselling relationship, students should take up responsibilities to participate fully, cooperatively and willingly (Gibson & Mariane, 2006).

Table 6: Effectiveness of Individual Counselling in Enhancing Discipline among Students

Statements	Responses (percent)					
	SA	A	NS	D	SD	TOTAL
Individual counselling helped reduce cases of school dropout, and enhanced discipline	61.4	24.4	7.1	5.5	1.6	100.0 (127)
Individual counselling helps improve relationship with prefects and school authority	37.8	42.5	7.9	7.9	3.9	100.0 (127)
Individual counselling has helped reduce cases of failure to complete assignments	45.7	34.6	11.0	5.5	3.1	100.0 (127)
Direct relationship with the counsellor helped students change behaviour positively	46.5	40.2	7.1	3.1	3.1	100.0 (127)

Effectiveness of Group Counselling in Enhancing Discipline among Students

Table 7 indicates that 46.8% strongly agreed that group counselling was effective in enabling them share experiences, thus helped to reduce indiscipline cases. Concerning truancy, 35.4% strongly agreed while 45.7% agreed that group counselling had effectively reduced the cases with 5.5% not sure and strongly disagreeing respectively. This implies that group counselling should be encouraged among students to enhance discipline because groups have rules and each member is supposed to conform to them as they share experiences. Bakhda (2004) observes that group counselling was vital in preventing disturbances among students while

helping to develop a free and friendly atmosphere while Wangombe (2008) observes high handed administration, lack of guidance and rigid rules as some of the causes for the increasing cases of student unrest and indiscipline.

The study notes that students should be offered an opportunity to share experiences and help others makes group counselling a powerful tool for enhancing discipline among members. Schools should establish conducive and acceptable environments in which to avail opportunities for interaction, self -disclosure and receive feedback.

Table 7: Effectiveness of Group Counselling in Enhancing Discipline among Students

Statements	Responses (percent)					
	SA	A	NS	D	SD	TOTAL
Group counselling enables students to share experiences thus reduce indiscipline cases	46.8	34.6	2.4	7.1	7.1	100.0 (127)
Group counselling has helped improve attendance and truancy among students reduced	35.4	45.7	6.3	3.1	6.3	100.0 (127)
Group counselling has made students aware of the consequences of their actions thus enhancing discipline	38.6	49.6	5.5	3.1	5.5	100.0 (127)

Group counselling has helped reduce negative peer influences and discipline has improved	45.7	40.2	5.5	4.7	5.5	100.0 (127)
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Cross-tabulation of students' responses on the effectiveness and rating of the types of guidance and counselling

Cross tabulation of responses presented in Table 8 indicate that 33 (25.98%) students rated individual counselling as very effective, 26 (20.47%) as moderate, 3 (2.36%) and 2(1.57%) very low. Peer counselling very high and moderate each by 14 (11.02%) while group counselling rated by 35(27.56%) with 11 (8.66%) students for very high, 19(14.96%) moderate, 2 (1.57%) and 3(2.36%) for very low respectively (Appendix E presents summation of individual scores and means).

The study notes that individual type of counselling was rated by 64(50.39%) of the students, peer and group types of counselling by 28 (22.04%) and 35 (27.56%) respectively. The responses indicate that students were more responsive to individual counselling as opposed to peer and group counselling types. This qualifies Kibui's (2005) observation that peer

and group types of counselling be strengthened in schools as they would help reach more students in the absence of adequately trained guidance and counselling personnel thus improve students' perception of the guidance and counselling services, hence transform them positively.

Responses on peer and group types of counselling point towards the need to provide knowledge and skills in handling students, problems in order to enhance discipline in schools. The researcher observes that, individual type of counselling was rated as most effective 47.85% followed by group and peer types of counselling at 42.13% and 37.98% respectively. These percentages present the mean level of students' discipline at 42.65% explaining why riots and strikes were common in the area the study.

Table 8: Rating Effectiveness of Types of Guidance and Counselling in Enhancing Discipline

Effectiveness	Rating	Types of Guidance and Counselling			
		Individual counselling	Peer counselling	Group counselling	Total
Which types of guidance and counselling do you employ towards enhancing discipline among students?					
How would you rate	Very high	33	14	11	58
The effectiveness of the types of guidance and counselling used for enhancing discipline among students?	Moderate	26	14	19	59
	Low	3	0	2	5
	Very Low	2	0	3	5

Total	64	28	35	127
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Cross - tabulation of Teacher Counsellors’ responses on the Effectiveness and Rating of Guidance and Counselling Types in Enhancing Discipline

Table 9 presents the teacher counsellors on their rating of the effectiveness of the types of guidance and counselling in enhancing discipline. The terms of rating were “very high, high and moderate” The table indicates that 3 out of 10 teacher counsellors used the said terms in rating individual type of counselling whereas only one rated peer and group types of counselling as highly effective respectively.

Their responses indicate individual type of counselling as the most effective in enhancing discipline among students. The responses imply that there was need to strengthen peer and group counselling types to enable more students benefit from the counselling services offered in schools

Table 9: Teacher Counsellors’ Rating of Effectiveness of Types Counselling in Enhancing Discipline

Effectiveness	Rating	Types of Guidance and Counselling					Total
		Individual Type	Peer type	Group type	Peer and individual	All the types	
Which types of guidance and counselling do you employ for enhancing discipline among students?							
How would you rate the effectiveness of the types of guidance and counselling used for enhancing discipline among students?	Very high	1	0	0	2	1	4
	High	1	1	1	1	0	4
	Moderate	1	0	0	0	1	2
Total		3	1	1	3	2	10

Conclusion

The study established that individual, peer and group types of counselling were employed in schools but had not been effective in enhancing discipline among students. It was further

established that most students rated the effectiveness of individual counselling highly followed by group and peer types respectively, an indication that training in counselling knowledge, skills and techniques had not been

adequate. The study observed that teachers in charge of guidance and counselling were aware of their role in enhancing school discipline though inadequately trained and this resulted in ineffective provision of guidance and counselling services to the students.

Recommendations

The government should develop a strategy of harmonizing coordinating and supervising guidance and counselling services to ensure there is effective and continuous provision of the services in secondary schools towards enhancing discipline among students. Guidance and counselling programme should be revitalized in all schools by providing with trained counsellors whose main preoccupation would be provision of counselling services to students.

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The Ministry of Education Science and Technology should frequently organize workshops, seminars and courses for teacher counsellors in order to equip them with the necessary knowledge, skills and techniques to enable them provide effective guidance and counselling, thus enhance discipline among secondary school students.

Resources, materials, reference books and facilities including policy guidelines should be provided to help students improve their behaviour positively, thus enhance discipline among students.

Discipline committees in schools should work hand in hand with the guidance and counselling departments in addressing school discipline issues. More research is needed focusing on the roles of school heads and boards of management in enhancing school discipline.

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